

The data uploaded contain five tables in total. Tables 1-2 summarize mineralogical composition of the thirteen saline mineral dust samples investigated in this work, and Tables 3-5 summarize mass hygroscopic growth factors of these samples as a function of relative humidity (RH, from <1% to 90%).

Table 1. Mineralogical composition of XJ-1, XJ-2, XJ-3, XJ-4, XJ-5 and XJ-6. The mass fractions of each minerals (in %, relative to all the minerals identified by XRD) are provided here.

mineral	XJ-1	XJ-2	XJ-3	XJ-4	XJ-5	XJ-6
quartz	16	24	13	34	5	4
orthoclase	6	10	0	25	17	24
albite	56	44	20	24	0	0
muscovite	9	11	0	0	0	0
calcite	3	6	4	3	0	30
aragonite	0	0	48	0	0	0
kaolinite	4	3	9	0	0	0
chlorite	0	0	0	0	0	0
illite	0	0	0	0	0	0
hematite	0	0	6	0	0	0
goethite	3	2	0	7	0	0
pyrite	0	0	0	0	14	0
anhydrite	0	0	0	0	0	27
thenardite	0	0	0	0	0	0
halite	5	0	2	7	63	14
rutile	0	0	0	0	0	0

Table 2. Mineralogical composition of IM-1, IM-2, IM-3, QH, NX, SX and SD. The mass fractions of each minerals (% , relative to all the minerals identified by XRD) are provided here.

mineral	IM-1	IM-2	IM-3	QH	NX	SX	SD
quartz	44	29	21	41	0	24	43
orthoclase	14	12	21	11	51	10	20
albite	13	29	5	20	0	44	0
muscovite	15	0	0	17	0	11	0
calcite	4	2	23	2	0	6	10
aragonite	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
kaolinite	5	2	1	4	0	3	0
chlorite	0	13	19	0	0	0	0
illite	0	3	0	0	0	0	0
hematite	0	0	2	0	0	0	0
goethite	5	0	0	4	0	2	0
pyrite	0	0	0	0	34	0	9
anhydrite	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
thenardite	0	0	6	0	0	0	0
halite	0	9	0	0	15	0	17
rutile	0	0	3	0	0	0	0

Table 3. Mass growth factors as a function of RH for JX-1, XJ-2, XJ-3, XJ-4 and XJ-5. All the experiments were repeated for three times, and the average values and corresponding standard deviations were reported.

RH (%)	XJ-1	XJ-2	XJ-3	XJ-4	XJ-5
<1	1.0000±0.0001	1.0000±0.0001	1.0000±0.0001	1.0000±0.0001	1.0000±0.0001
10	1.0030±0.0003	1.0040±0.0001	1.0044±0.0002	1.0017±0.0001	1.0013±0.0002
20	1.0049±0.0003	1.0065±0.0001	1.0075±0.0003	1.0029±0.0001	1.0023±0.0005
30	1.0067±0.0003	1.0085±0.0001	1.0104±0.0002	1.0041±0.0002	1.0032±0.0007
40	1.0085±0.0003	1.0105±0.0001	1.0130±0.0003	1.0054±0.0004	1.0040±0.0013
50	1.0106±0.0003	1.0125±0.0001	1.0158±0.0003	1.0069±0.0005	1.0054±0.0013
60	1.0138±0.0002	1.0147±0.0001	1.0189±0.0006	1.0089±0.0008	1.0077±0.0015
70	1.0267±0.0002	1.0173±0.0001	1.0345±0.0007	1.0169±0.0006	1.0359±0.0060
80	1.2676±0.0023	1.0215±0.0001	1.1094±0.0018	1.3880±0.0008	3.0888±0.0119
90	1.6569±0.0053	1.0312±0.0001	1.2602±0.0030	1.7183±0.0071	4.9258±0.0139

Table 4. Mass growth factors as a function of RH for JX-6, IM-1, IM-2 and IM-3. All the experiments were repeated for three times, and the average values and corresponding standard deviations were reported.

RH (%)	XJ-6	IM-1	IM-2	IM-3
0	1.0000±0.0001	1.0000±0.0001	1.0000±0.0001	1.0000±0.0001
10	1.0021±0.0001	1.0023±0.0001	1.0007±0.0001	1.0011±0.0001
20	1.0035±0.0001	1.0037±0.0001	1.0013±0.0001	1.0018±0.0001
30	1.0048±0.0001	1.0050±0.0005	1.0020±0.0005	1.0026±0.0001
40	1.0069±0.0001	1.0059±0.0002	1.0024±0.0008	1.0030±0.0003
50	1.0118±0.0001	1.0072±0.0002	1.0030±0.0010	1.0037±0.0003
60	1.0137±0.0002	1.0095±0.0002	1.0040±0.0008	1.0046±0.0003
70	1.0166±0.0001	1.0192±0.0003	1.0137±0.0019	1.0093±0.0005
80	1.0204±0.0001	1.0503±0.0007	1.3350±0.0026	1.1431±0.0031
90	1.1212±0.0048	1.1237±0.0008	1.7353±0.0165	1.9732±0.0200

Table 5. Mass growth factors as a function of RH for QH, NX, SX and SD. All the experiments were repeated for three times, and the average values and corresponding standard deviations were reported.

RH (%)	QH	NX	SX	SD
0	1.0000±0.0001	1.0000±0.0001	1.000±0.00010	1.0000±0.0001
10	1.0022±0.0001	1.0001±0.0001	1.0030±0.0001	1.0067±0.0003
20	1.0037±0.0001	1.0003±0.0005	1.0049±0.0001	1.0157±0.0004
30	1.0049±0.0001	1.0004±0.0004	1.0062±0.0001	1.0302±0.0024
40	1.0060±0.0001	1.0005±0.0005	1.0074±0.0001	1.0410±0.0022
50	1.0072±0.0001	1.0006±0.0005	1.0087±0.0002	1.0542±0.0015
60	1.0086±0.0001	1.0009±0.0007	1.0102±0.0002	1.0765±0.0022
70	1.0104±0.0001	1.0121±0.0011	1.0119±0.0002	1.1603±0.0074
80	1.0134±0.0001	4.0823±0.0081	1.0146±0.0002	1.4369±0.0250
90	1.0215±0.0001	6.7060±0.0227	1.0212±0.0003	1.7910±0.0471